

Support multi-object forest management plans through easy-access information

Introduction

To support sustainable forest management aimed at maximizing ecosystem services through new silvicultural practices, it is essential to have access to a range of information that enables forest managers to quickly retrieve data, with the ultimate goal of achieving certification for ecosystem services.

In this context, PRI.FOR.MAN, which has developed a decision support system in the Friuli Venezia Giulia region, provides various user-friendly graphical interface access to diverse information. In this context PRI.FOR.MAN DSS provide user-friendly information regarding (i) the Forest Types Categories that define the classification of forested areas based on specific criteria such as land use, productivity, conservation; (ii) Availability of Existing Forest Management Plans, that outline strategies and objectives for the sustainable management of forest resources in a specific area, that guide management actions over time; (iii) Forest Roads: The network of forest roads is vital for accessibility and forest area management not just for wood mobilization but also for touristic activities; (iv) Annual Growth of wood: This value indicates the average annual growth of forest resources and influences the capacity of resource renewal; (v) Presence of Disturbances: This may include events like fires, diseases, or insect infestations that affect tree health and require specific management actions; (vi) Environmental Constraints: These encompass considerations related to environmental conservation and protection, (vii) Protective Role of Forest Vegetation: This concerns the significance of forest vegetation in providing ecosystem services such as soil protection and water cycle regulation; (viii) Location of Biotopes, Parks, and Regional or State Reserves: These are ecologically significant sites or protected areas requiring special management for biodiversity conservation; (ix) Natura 2000 Sites: These are designated sites within the European Union's Natura 2000 network, necessitating specific conservation and development measures based on prevailing regulations.

All these elements are fundamental for sustainable forest management, which aims to balance the utilization of forest resources with the conservation of the natural environment. They provide essential information for forest managers to develop multi-objective forest management plans and actions that are not only linked with wood mobilization but also with biodiversity conservation, tourist activities, and the monitoring of forest health. Before the PRI.FOR.MAN, this information was already available online but scattered across various local authority websites. The PRI.FOR.MAN project has allowed for the consolidation of these data into a single container, the Decision Support System (DSS), designed specifically for the forest context.

Lessons learned

Harmonizing information and making it available in user-friendly systems is crucial to ensure data accessibility. Otherwise, users trying to navigate across different portals may struggle to access the information, leading to its underutilization. Without the use of information, it becomes challenging to plan multi-objective management strategies, and there's a risk of abandonment of forested areas.

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Further information

https://lookerstudio.google.com/u/0/reporting/2f6c2f81-b78f-446c-ab07-96571d7b6984/page/p_w5k3gvls6c

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